

Spot Treatment of Clethodim for Control of Weedy Rice

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Introduction

- Weedy rice (*Oryza sativa* f. *spontanea* Roshev.) is an emerging weed in California rice production systems.
- Spot spray herbicide applications can be a useful approach to control weedy rice.
- There are no labeled herbicides for control of weedy rice in California.
- Clethodim, an ACCase inhibiting herbicide, is a potential candidate due to its effective activity on weedy rice and conventional rice, which was determined in preliminary studies.

Objectives

- To evaluate the efficacy of clethodim as a spot spray application in conventional rice
- Determine the effect of clethodim dispersion after a spot spray application

Figure 1. Clethodim dose response on weedy rice accessions, from preliminary work.

Materials and Methods

- M209 rice was seeded on two fields, north field and south field, at the Rice Experiment Station Biggs, CA
- At each field, two spot spray applications of clethodim at 150 (1x) and 300 g ai ha⁻¹ (2x) was applied with five replications in a randomized complete block design
- The application area was 100 by 50 cm
- Application was made at the tillering stage
- Clethodim (Select Max, Valent LLC, San Ramon, CA) efficacy through visual injury was evaluated in the application zone, 0-25 cm surrounding the original application, and 25-50 cm surrounding the original application
- The expanding injury level was measured in cm from the original application area and compared among rates
- Data was subjected to ANOVA and mean comparison with LSD at an $\alpha=0.05$

Figure 2. Applying clethodim with a 2-nozzle sprayer and CO₂ backpack.

Results

Figure 3. Efficacy of clethodim on M209 rice after a spot spray application in a 100 by 50 cm area at the 1x and 2x rates in the north and south field. Values with a different letter are significantly different with a least significant difference at $\alpha=0.05$. P value <0.01.

Table 1. Dispersion effect of clethodim injury from the original application area after a spot spray application on M209 rice.

Clethodim rate g-ai-ha ⁻¹	Field	Expanding Injury from Application Area cm	Injury in First Dispersion Area		Injury in Second Dispersion Area	
			%		%	
			0-25 cm	25-50 cm	0-25 cm	25-50 cm
150	South	104 by 46	0 b	0	0	0
300	South	122 by 56	8 a	0	0	0
150	North	100 by 50	0 b	0	0	0
300	North	100 by 60	7 a	0	0	0
CV (%)			1.52	-	-	-
P value			<0.01	-	-	-

Application area 100 by 50 cm; values with a different letter are significantly different with a least significant difference at $\alpha=0.05$.

Figure 4. Left, spot spray dispersion area of clethodim (black: spot spray area, green: 0-25cm dispersion area, red: 25-50cm dispersion area). Right, measuring the expanding injury from the application area.

Discussion and Conclusion

- There were differences in clethodim efficacy across location, but overall, all over 73%.
- There was minimal to no injury in the first dispersion area and no injury in the second dispersion area, demonstrating clethodim doesn't readily disperse and won't cause extensive injury in a spot spray.
- Clethodim as a spot spray application has potential to be a tool for control of weedy rice in conventional rice.

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